

Development of tourism in Uzbekistan. The place of pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan and other countries of the world

Shakhnoza Eshonkulova

Annotation:

In the Middle Ages, mainly pilgrim trips were carried out. Religious beliefs led millions of Muslims to holy Mecca, Christians to Jerusalem and Rome, the rest to other pilgrim places. The church first founded the hotel system. The medieval renaissance is of particular importance for the development of pilgrim tourism.

Keywords:

Religious travel, religious beliefs, state tourism, pilgrim tourism activities.

Information about the authors

Shakhnoza Eshonkulova

*"Silk Road" International
University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, in the development of international tourism in the countries of the world, great attention is paid to increasing the socio-economic importance of tourist enterprises. In order to ensure that a broad segment of the population will actively contribute to the tourism sector, which has become one of the four priority sectors in the world, that is, they will participate on a large scale in the organization of various tourist services, and as a result, they will increase the social and economic interests of the countries. the role of private tourist enterprises and organizations is extremely important.

Currently, about 60,000 small enterprises with different forms of ownership are operating in our republic. 96.1% of these enterprises are privately owned enterprises. Small enterprises account for 96% of total products, works and services. As can be seen from the data, the state attaches great importance to the development of private and small entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Private tourism enterprises, which are of decisive importance in the development of tourism, as in other sectors, can be conditionally divided into two types: companies that directly receive tourists and organize their trips, and those that indirectly affect the development of tourism. small and private business entities. The first category includes small tourist companies, private hotels, camping sites, transport companies, restaurants, etc., and the second category includes local small and private enterprises that produce products of a traditional-national character, craft enterprises, and the like.

It is known that tourists visiting the country demand a certain amount of products and services, from simple food to expensive souvenirs. This naturally opens the way for small and private business enterprises engaged in the production of products and services to further expand their capabilities. Farmers grow clean products in hotels where tourists stay, small and private enterprises operating in the textile and garment industry develop bedroom furniture, bathrobes and the like necessary for tourists, cosmetics industry enterprises produce shampoo, soap and deodorants. they release Craft workshops and enterprises producing traditional national products also prepare orders for tourists. In general, the activity

of private tourist enterprises in the republic's tourism industry is not significant. The main reasons for this are as follows:[1]

First of all, the fact that some companies operating in the field of tourism in the republic have a monopoly character. Due to certain reasons, the process of privatization of the objects of these companies is being carried out rather slowly. In addition, some of the newly established small tourism firms do not have many of the opportunities available in large tourism companies;

Secondly, due to the lack of highly qualified personnel in the field of tourism, the establishment and efficient operation of new small tourism firms is becoming a very urgent problem;

Thirdly, as a result of the inability of the officials working in the local representative bodies in most of the regions and districts of the republic to correctly assess the contribution of tourism to the economy and their old-fashioned approach to work, the establishment of tourist companies, as well as an indirect impact on the tourism market the opening of small and private tourism enterprises that show;

Fourthly, newly established tourism companies are limited to a narrow scope of activity. In addition, they do not go beyond certain types of services that are considered traditional for the national company "Uzbekturizm". As a result, these companies are not sufficiently recognized by foreign tourists.

If tourism companies offer non-traditional types of services, for example, organizing wonderful trips to the beautiful and beautiful nature of our country, organizing tours for tourists to introduce them to the national customs of the people in local villages and villages, as well as concerts in the national spirit for tourists and they can achieve their goals if they organize services such as organizing shows.

Fifth, the production of local handicraft products, national spirit clothes, national food and so on is one of the most urgent issues.

As we noted above, private tourist companies are extremely important for the rapid and high-quality development of the market of tourism services. Due to the fact that the tourism infrastructure suitable for the market economy is now developing in our country, almost all private tourist companies are small business entities. According to the assessment of foreign experts, the peace prevailing in Uzbekistan, the antiques, ancient cultural monuments and beautiful nature of our country make it possible for 2-2.5 million tourists to visit the country every year. Today, one of the most important sectors of international tourism is religious tourism. The history of the formation of religious tourism goes back a long way. That is, its first appearance dates back to antiquity. The main places of origin of religious tourism are the homeland of the ancient Greeks and Romans. In ancient times, the Greeks and Romans built temples and churches and worshiped in them. The most famous temple in Hellas was first built in Delphax. This temple was the most famous and great in the whole Greek world, and the place of worship of the prophetic priest, who answered any question firmly in the name of God. Legend has it that thousands of dervishes came to the temple to listen to the prophecies of St. Pythagoras, the pagan priest who sacrificed himself. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION By the Middle Ages, the migration of religious tourism began to take on a new dimension. Visiting places of worship in the holy places of worship took on a mass character and took the form of crusades. In particular, the pilgrimage movement reached its peak in the XV century and the beginning of the XVI century. As the scope of the pilgrimage grew, so did its various streams. At the same time, the composition of the pilgrims was also diverse, in which, in addition to people of religious beliefs, there were also a variety of professionals, officials, people. Among the pilgrims were aristocrats, knights (nobles), travelers, soldiers, artists, government officials, merchants, and even ordinary people. By the 19th century, religious tourism began to take an organized form. It is estimated that the number of visitors increased steadily, reaching 300,000-400,000 in 1861 in France

alone. In the late 1870s, the flow of organized pilgrimage also expanded in several European countries, such as Austria and Germany. Today, in different parts of the world, as in many centuries ago, the number of tourists visiting religious sites is growing. Every year, 200 million More than a dozen people go on various religious pilgrimages. Of these, more than 150 million Christians, 20-30 million. Around it are Hindus, more than 40 million Muslims, Buddhists, Shintoists and others. The main purpose of the pilgrims' journey is to visit the saints, to be relieved during worship, to be purified of hearts, to be free from serious illnesses, to ask God for their sins, and to be spiritually close to their companions during the journey. On their journey, the pilgrims try to achieve their dreams, to give thanks to the Creator and to fulfill his honor. Today, there are more than 10 major centers of pilgrimage tourism in the world, located on almost all continents of Ershari: • Christian Europe; • North America, which is firmly rooted in Christianity and many other religions; • Latin America with Christianity and traditional religions; • North Africa that converted to Islam; • Islam is predominant and there are separate Christianity and traditional religions in West and East Africa; • Southeast Asia, dominated by Buddhism, Islam, Christianity, and Hinduism; • Central Asia strengthened by Buddhism (mainly Lamaism); • Islamic-dominated Central Asia; • Islam and Christianity, West Asia strengthened by Judaism; • Judaism and Buddhism are widespread, as well as Christianity, Jainism, Sikhism and Islam in South Asia. Each macroregion is famous primarily for its global centers of pilgrimage. They embrace the international flow of believers and are often combined with the functions of administrative, industrial, cultural and tourist centers of religious specialization. In addition, there are religious sites of national and local significance in the macroregions. One of the oldest and largest religious centers on the planet is the city of Jerusalem (Jerusalem) in the Middle East state of Jordan. Located on the right bank of the Jordan River, the area was occupied by Israel in 1967 in Greece. He is still in Jordan without being returned. It is known that the city of Jerusalem is the center of the origin and foundation of the three religions, namely, Christianity, Islam and Judaism. It occupies a special place among the centers of worship in the world. The city's past history goes back a long way. Here, monotheists (monotheism, that is, those who believe in one God) who first believed in Judaism, and later Christianity and Islam, testify to their origins. Jerusalem is a holy city for Christians. The largest place of pilgrimage in the city is the Church of the Resurrection. This temple is considered a sacred place of worship for believers of the Christian world all over the world. A tourist who is annoyed at every step will definitely try to visit this temple. Tourists who come here perform acts of worship such as worshipping the sacred Golgofe, worshipping the Pomazonian stones and the picturesque tomb of Allah. The church is worshiped by people of all nationalities and ethnic groups, including Jews, Armenians, Syrians, Abyssinians, Greeks, Italians, French, Germans, Russians, and all European nations. One of the largest religious centers in Europe is Rome. This ancient city is home to world-famous sabers. One of them is Laterano of San Javan, built in the IV century. She is glorified as "the mother of all the churches in Rome and on earth". It contains the Holy Monuments: St. Peter and Paul, the Jewish prophet Noah, Aaron's holy iron rod, Mary's veil, the part of the table where the Mysterious Evenings were held, and the "true cross" column. It has survived to our time. It was brought from the palace of Pilate in Jerusalem. Legend has it that he was taken to the execution of Jesus. The 28 marble stairs can only be climbed by bending the knees. Currently, San Javanniin-Laterano is the cathedral of Rome. Outside Rome is the Vatican City-State. It is the center of the Catholic Church, the residence of its leader, the Pope. The Vatican is home to priceless treasures of culture. In particular, the cathedral of St. Peter amazes with its splendor. Pilgrims from all over the world flock here. According to tradition, they perform the tawaf, kissing the feet of the famous statues of the

guiding Saints. Catholic holiday - Easter is especially busy in the Vatican. Pope wishes good luck to those gathered in St. Peter's Square. His eloquent speech, imbued with the spirit of obedience and prayer, deeply excites believers. The High Father of all Catholics listens to the divine words with all his heart. The list of Christian holy monuments and customs and traditions mentioned above does not end there. No other religion in the world is equal to Christianity in the variety and number of places and objects of divine worship. It should be noted that today in other parts of Europe, including Bruges, Belgium, Turin, Italy, Lourdes, France, and Jasna-Guru, Poland, the shrines attract millions of Christian pilgrims. According to legend, after the death of Jesus Christ, his body was wrapped in linen cloth, soaked in fragrant myrrh resin and olive oil, and placed in a cave on a rock. Because the shroud has been carefully preserved, Christians still worship it as a sacred shrine. By the middle of the 19th century, 42 original pieces of clothing belonging to Jesus Christ had been preserved: shoulder-length, sleeveless vests. Today, these vests are still housed in an elegant box armored with silver at the main cathedral in Turin, Italy. It is shown to the public once every 25 years. At that time, 3 million people came to Turin. Visitors come close. The last demonstration of the sacred object was held in 2003. People wait in line for more than 15-16 hours to see it. Another sacred object is a "drop of blood" belonging to Jesus Christ, which is kept in a prayer room in Bruges, Belgium. At one time, this sacred object was presented as a gift to the Patriarch (priest) of Jerusalem, Count Gerry of Alsace, Belgium. Nowadays, every Friday, a sacred "drop of blood" is displayed in a special crystal vessel on the feast of "Blood Day" and is performed by pilgrims. The festivities will take place all over the streets of Bruges and will be attended by tens of thousands of pilgrims. Buddhism is the third largest religion in the world after Christianity and Islam. Buddhism first appeared in the territory of ancient India before our era. It appeared in the IV-V centuries. It later spread to Southeast Asia, Central Asia, partly to Central Asia, and Siberia. Today, Buddhists worship at the holy city of Lhasa in the Himalayas, China. The city is located at an altitude of 3650 meters above sea level, where the Dalai Lama Monastery and a very large palace are located. This palace was built in the XVII century and consists of more than a thousand rooms. The palace has about ten thousand objects of worship and more than 20 thousand different statues. The Dalai Lama's Palace houses the World Buddhist Administration. Pilgrims visiting Mecca walk around the Kaaba seven times, starting from the corner where its Black Stone is poured, and make tawba. Pilgrims then ascend Safatag seven times and Mount Mawa seven times. After that, they will visit Mount Arafat and perform Hajj. Al-Haram, the largest miracle mosque in the Muslim world, built by the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, has been erected on the site of the Kaaba. The total number of pilgrims who come here every year to take part in the Eid al-Adha celebrations is 2 million. It exceeds man. Madinah is the burial city of the Prophet Muhammad and is located in the oasis of Al-Hamd. Pilgrims visit Madinah to visit the tomb of the Prophet after completing the Hajj. It should be noted that there are many places of pilgrimage in the Muslim world. In particular, in Central Asia, as well as in the Republic of Uzbekistan, there are countless places where saints live and are buried. These include the Mausoleum of Ahmad Yassavi in Turkestan, South Kazakhstan Province; Zangiota complex in Zangiota district of Tashkent region; Sheikh KhivandaTakhur Mausoleum in Tashkent, Kaldirgoch-Biya Mausoleum, Yunuskhan Mausoleum; Hazrat Imam Complex; Tomb of Abubakr Muhammad Kaffal Shashi; Tomb of Sheikh Zayniddin Bobo; Imam Al-Bukhari complex in Hartang village of Payarik district of Samarkand region; Makhtumi Azammaqbarasi in Dahbed fortress of Aqdarya district; Mausoleums of ShahiZinda, AmirTemur, Ruhobod, Khoja Daniel, Motrudiy, Murod avliyo, Khoja Ahror Vali, Oqsaroy, Choponota in Samarkand; Mausoleums of Ismail Samoni, Chashmai Ayub, Sadrididdin Buharzi, Bohovuddin

Naqshbandi, Buyon Kulikhon, Chor Bakr in Bukhara; Mausoleum of Uchavliyo, Said Allovuddin in Khorezm region; In Kashkadarya region - Jahongir, Dorus Saodat, Dorut Tilovat complex, Kokgumbaz mosque; In Surkhandarya region - Hakimat-Termizi complex; Sultan Saodat Temple Monument, Fayoztepa Temple; Sadr Vakhs Avliya (Avliyota) complex in Jizzakh region; In Fergana region, Dakhmon Shahon cemetery and Mazarikhan mausoleum are the places that attract tourists.

CONCLUSION

During the years of independence, the burial places and tombs of many saints and saints were restored and restored to their original state. These monuments have been transformed into beautiful, prosperous, pilgrimage places. Among them, the mausoleums of Saints and Imams such as Bahoviddin Naqshbandi, Gijduvani, ImamBukhari, Makhtumi Azam, Shahizinda, Motrudi, Hakimat-Termizi, Zangiota have become unique places of pilgrimage and spiritual inspiration for Muslims.

REFERENCE

1. Kimelev Yu.A. Modern Western Philosophy of Religion. Moscow 1999
2. Philosophy of religion // Eastern philosophy. Tash GIV, 2006
3. Vasiliev V.V. History of the Religion of the East. Hegel. Philosophy of religion. Moscow, 1976
4. Fundamentals of modern philosophy. Moscow, 1999 (electronic version)